

Artificial Intelligence in enhancing Hybrid mode of Teaching Educators perspective across Bengaluru City

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Abstract – Responding to the pandemic, universities have been making great strides to improve their students' online learning experiences. Still, more effort is required, as it always has been. In response to the COVID-19 outbreak, educational institutions hastened to improve their online course offerings. A lot of universities have made the hasty decision that it's best to create an online environment that's almost identical to the real thing. The decision by some colleges to return to online learning for the last days of the term highlights the need of institutions becoming ready for the future of flexible, hybrid learning, since there has been a significant uptick in these cases. Artificial intelligence (AI) and other types of educational technology may have a significant impact on how schools are structured in the years to come. It is the hope of the proposed research that AI and other forms of educational technology can facilitate a smoother shift from conventional to hybrid classrooms and, by extension, better instruction for students. The project will gather data from the educators using quantitative approaches and a descriptive research style. A master validity statistic-validated, well-structured questionnaire will serve as the data collection tool. A non-probability sampling technique will be used to choose the sample, with a margin of error of 7%. The research will involve two hundred teachers. For the purpose of data analysis, SPSS and AMOS will be utilised. Based on the study's findings, AI has a major influence on improving hybrid teaching, and different demographics of educators have diverse perspectives on hybrid teaching.

Keywords – Artificial Intelligence, Hybrid Teaching, Teacher experiences, Artificial Intelligence in Education.

I. INTRODUCTION

For the past 40 years, numerous titles have been used to refer to what is now known as Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIED), the most popular of which being Intelligent Tutoring Systems. Papers published in a special edition of the International Journal of ManMachine Studies [1], a book based on those papers [2,3], and early works in the field of artificial intelligence all contributed to the discipline's initial exposure to a wider audience [2].

This area of study has used, and continues to use, methods from AI and cognitive science to investigate the dynamics of learning and instruction, with the ultimate goal of creating systems that help students learn and retain information in ways that are analogous to receiving individualized, insightful, and adaptable guidance from a knowledgeable human instructor. In other words, adaptive learning systems try to adjust their teaching methods based on students' prior knowledge and abilities, their preferred methods of studying, and their emotional trajectories when they encounter the inevitable difficulties associated with learning something new. While there is undoubtedly some overlap with other uses of computing technology in education, what sets this approach apart is its dedication to individual adaptation by modelling various components of the learning process.

In order to provide education and training, "e-learning" [4] refers to the use of Artificial intelligence for education communication. A system's e-learning capabilities are those that allow for the electronic distribution, administration, support, and supervision of instructional contents [5]. Despite its name, "e-learning" (or "online learning")

includes far more than just instruction delivered by digital media [6]. Electronic technology and the learning experience are the two pillars of e-learning. Both the medium and the approach to education are together known as "e-Learning". The prevalence of online education has increased in recent years.

E-low learning's overhead and widespread accessibility have made this possible. Educational and training institutions have embraced e-learning by implementing an ever-growing list of technology-enabled platforms [7] due to its many benefits, including greater flexibility (in terms of time, place, and length of training), greater access to instructors, and lower overall costs associated with course delivery and management. The World Health Organization found in their systematic review that e-learning is superior to traditional methods of education in 29% of knowledge improvement studies and 40% of skill improvement studies. Hybrid learning or otherwise known as blended learning is the mix of face to face classroom instruction and online instruction. Machine learning is an effective method which can be incorporated in the hybrid learning model, which is why this discussion will focus on the failure factors of the approach and how AI can be used to support blended learning.

That would be one of the main advantages of the further implementation of AI into the already existing hybrid learning model for students. It can identify a student's learning profile including their preferred modalities of learning, and then adapt the content and teaching methods to this profile. This could involve changing the level of the difficulty, suggesting material or working with a student, offering feedbacks that would improve the performance.

When combined with human resources, AI makes it easier to call for differentiated instructions, in ways that will make it easy to meet the needs of hard-to-teach students, or students with learning disabilities, among other learning barriers.

Another angle that AI can complement the hybrid learning model with is by incorporating intelligent tutoring systems. These systems involve application of Artificial Intelligence to give students feedback and directions on what to do. It goes without saying that ITS can be rather effective in blended learning contexts, as the system can augment the instruction that is given by teachers and offer further assistance to the students outside of the learning context. This could thus assist in enhancing the student progresses, as students are made to gain more time and attention from their tutors.

AI can also serve as an instrument in communication between students and teachers and in working with students who study remotely due to the coronavirus pandemic. For instance, an AI can be utilised as a chatbot assisting students and answering their inquiries as well as an AI-aided virtual classroom can be used for real time learning, sharing, and exchanging of information among the students and teacher. It is these tools which may make a difference and help to ensure that students are able to interact with the course material or with each other within the Unit and where necessary within a classroom where they physically encounter each other.

One more way that AI may help improve the form of a learning process in a hybrid environment is the usage of adaptive learning technologies. These technologies employ algorithms that are used to review a student's performance, depending on it the curriculum is modified. This could assist in providing information in regards to the form of instruction that would be best suited for the students' needs and also the areas that the students are having difficulties in. The adaptive learning technologies can also offer teachers insights into the student's progress and they may gain the ability to make properly informed decisions on the instruction approach to use as well as the overall support to offer.

Lastly there can be enhancement of the administrative part of the hybrid learning model by using knowledge of and elements of artificial intelligence. For instance, through AI, it is possible to analyse the students' performance trends and patterns so that the administrators make the right decisions on resource distribution and program development. Another use of AI is to minimize routine activities like scheduling or monitoring attendance, therefore minimizing time spent on these activities can save hours each day for teachers and administrators.

Altogether, AI has the potential of offering a great contribution to the development of the hybrid learning model in the education sector. As smart education assistants, intelligent tutoring systems, enablers of

communication and collaboration, promoters of adaptive learning technologies, and enablers of enhanced administration, AI can raise student performance and optimise the learning process. With the progressive use of technology in different fields, education cannot be left behind and indeed we are likely to experience even better use of AI in education in the near future. Moreover the hybrid learning model stands to benefit from this advancement.

The current study is an aim to understand how Artificial intelligence and educational technology can improve the teaching experience and enhance the current transition in learning environments from traditional learning to hybrid learning.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Whenever a society faces new social, political, or economic issues, its educational system adapts to meet the new demands [8]. This dynamic force, combined with an ever-expanding global community, necessitates stakeholders' ongoing evaluation and validation of what constitutes effective learning and teaching, a process that leads to the formulation and implementation of both national curriculum reforms and locally-conceived pedagogical innovations. [9,10]

The incorporation of Artificial Intelligence into the curriculum is receiving more and more attention among the many novel concepts that educational institutions must now consider. "The last two decades have seen a shift in educational reform attempts toward a greater focus on curricular standards and the need of having the many components of the education system work together to reinforce one another [11]. Consequently, there has been a resurgence of curiosity in finding ways to integrate Artificial Intelligence into educational content." As a result, ICT integration into educational curricula has begun to gain momentum throughout the globe. [12]

Multiple teaching and learning approaches in the subject of Commerce and Management have emerged as a direct result of technological advancements and Artificial Intelligence, and they have taken on very various forms at the primary, secondary, and university levels [13]. As noted by Bach, Haynes, and Smith (2006) [9], there is a pressing need to increase access to higher education for people throughout the world, and this has led to a focus on the potential benefits of online learning in the context of tertiary education.

Any change has the potential to either pave the way for innovation or mark the end of a long and arduous quest. Covid 19 is more of a lifestyle disruptor than a true epidemic. Everything about how people lived their lives shifted. Everything we did, from the time we woke up to the time we went to bed, from the way we sipped our coffee or tea to the way we read the news to the way we shopped to the way we adapted to a new health regime, had a dash of

creativity and an attitude to accept change[14]. Businesses began to take deliberate measures to cope with this downside once periodic lockdowns became a visible weapon in the fight against Covid 19. Almost every sector took a hit, and the survival of most would depend on a swift recovery. In terms of students' access to classroom discussions, the educational sector saw a dramatic change from a holistic to a minimalistic framework[15].

The use of virtual or online platforms is now widely accepted. Although this decision was seen as groundbreaking, it did not come without its share of difficulties. While the new system of education guaranteed continuity, it sacrificed human efficiency when dealing with difficult subject matter. The quality of information transfer was diminished due to a decrease in student-teacher interactions. Teachers are constantly being assessed, and as a result, many have revised their methods of teaching and set new objectives for themselves. Teachers, who are the backbone of any school, have to adjust their methods of instruction to meet the demands of an online environment[16]. Teaching fundamentals are increasingly centred on the instructor's comfort and competence using technological tools. Artificial Intelligence has opened up new possibilities for expanding one's reach and expanding one's business in this never-ending competition [17].

The educational sector has adopted the practice of working after normal business hours, which was formerly a phenomena exclusive to other industries. Stress levels among educators have risen dramatically as a result of students' increased reliance on electronic media and the accompanying demands for greater academic achievement. Workplace stress can be mitigated by a combination of physical and mental health[18].

Due to the 24/7 nature of the internet, less time is spent being physically active and more time is spent sitting at a desk, both of which undermine efforts to promote health and wellness. The promotion of positive mental health practices has long been recognized as a very important goal. Covid 19 has dramatically exacerbated the already serious mental health problems that many educators face. It has become a mammoth undertaking to balance teaching, research, and secondary responsibilities; to keep up with the new Hybrid teaching method; to deal with peer pressure; to meet government criteria; and to do any of these things well [9].

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The epidemic prompted a transition to the more difficult blended learning model. Due of the lack of a traditional classroom setting, Hybrid learning necessitates the extensive use of digital resources to meet the needs of students' education. There are perks and downsides to using these digital technologies. The use of such tools has far-reaching implications for education, including the expansion of hybrid and online formats. Therefore, it is

helpful to grasp the benefits of mixed teaching approaches by looking at the results of the methods used.

Multiple studies have found that Hybrid learning has a positive effect on students' psychological well-being. In order to know if Hybrid Teaching is harmful to teachers' mental health or supportive, it is important to have a firm grasp on how those involved in education experience the process.

IV. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To examine the impact of demographic variables of educators on the perception of Hybrid teaching
- To analyse the impact of Artificial Intelligence on Hybrid teaching

V. RESEARCH METHODS

Table 1 – Research methods

Research Type	The study is descriptive in nature, uses quantitative data from the educators to fulfil the objectives of the study.
Data collection Instrument	A well-structured questionnaire was prepared by taking continuous advice from the subject matter experts. The questionnaire was designed with 5 Demographic variables. 5 statements measuring Hybrid learning and 7 statements measuring impact of AI on Hybrid learning in form of Likert scale. The scale validity and reliability was affirmed. The Composite reliability is 0.877, Average variance explained is 0.567 and the square root of AVE was greater than the inter item correlations
Sample Size	The current study uses a convenience sample of 200 educators from Commerce and Management degree college across Bangalore city
Pilot study	Pilot study was carried by considering experts in field of education and technology to derive at the questionnaire
Plan of analysis	ANOVA and Independent t test -SPSS Vers 25 SEM – AMOS r Vers23

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- H1: There is a significant impact of demographic variables of educators on the perception of Hybrid teaching
- Table 2 – Statistical test Results for Hypothesis 1

	ANOVA- F Statistics				Indep enden t t test
Demographi c Variables	Age	Quali ficati on	Marit al Status	Mont hly	Gend er

				Incom e	
I am comfortable with Hybrid teaching	3.334	3.687	0.565	0.659	6.196
Hybrid teaching enhances teaching experience	4.922	1.835	0.151	3.034	4.547

- Hybrid teaching items are statistically significant for at least one of the Age groups at p value =.000. The scheffe post hoc results show that employees who are in age group of above 45 years have lower acceptance and less comfortable with Hybrid teaching .
- Hybrid teaching item is statistically significant for at least one of the Qualification groups at p value =.000.
- Hybrid teaching items are insignificant for marital status and Monthly Income..
- In case of gender, only Hybrid teaching comfort is statistically significant and female have higher comfort as compared to men while using Hybrid learning.

Therefore, Alternate Hypothesis, There is a significant impact of demographic variables of educators on the perception of Hybrid teaching is accepted

Age can make a significant contribution to how lecturers regard hybrid learning. These suggests that the older educators who were used to conventional face-to-face classroom teaching and learning may not have it easy with the hybrid learning model. They may finding the integration of technology and the delivery of online and blended face to face components a challenge. Meanwhile the young lectures, who have incorporated technology in their lives and are relatively more familiar with the virtual space, may effectively incorporate the hybrid learning model and replicate it to their benefit.

Secondly, gender could also affect their perception of hybrid learning among lecturers. Compared to age and qualifications, gender might be less of issue, but it still could be an issue. Some researchers have established that female students may be more inclined towards collaborative and cooperative learning techniques that would fit well in the hybrid learning approach. While males indicated more interest in factual content, it might suggest that knowledge delivery patterns that are more teacher directed might be less easily translated in the blended learning environment.

Finally, the expertise of the lecturers in the programme also greatly influences their attitudes towards the hybrid learning model. Another potential reason is that teachers, who have master’s degrees or who have completed additional training in educational technology, are likely to be more self-efficacious about using hybrid learning approaches. On the other hand, the inexperienced or less

trained instructors may find themselves struggling and having a low self-efficacy regarding handling the hybrid learning model.

Overall, it can be stated that age, gender and qualifications can play an important role in attitudes of the lecturers towards the hybrid learning model. It will also be relatively difficult for experienced lecturers, particularly those in the older age bracket to incorporate this new teaching style than the younger and more experienced ones. Moreover, the gender may become the factor affecting the choice of the lecturers and their approach in the context of hybrid learning model. In conclusion, and as has been depicted in the course of this paper, it is incumbent upon institutions to ensure sufficient support and resource provision to all lecturers regarding support dealing with the opportunities as well as the obstacles that can characterise hybrid learning.

- H2 –There is an impact of Artificial Intelligence on Hybrid teaching

The Chi-Square value of 765.091 with 136 degrees of freedom indicates a good fit of the data, while the p value of 0.00 indicates statistical significance. This is the result obtained by the CFA. Root Mean Square Error Approximation (RMSEA) = 0.031 and Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) = 0.922 both indicate that the model is very close to meeting the required requirements of fitness for good.

Table 3 – Structural relationship between variables

			Unstd estimate	Std Estimate	P value
Hybrid Teaching	←	Artificial Intelligence	0.632	0.598	***

1 Time increase in Artificial intelligence in education associated with a 0.632 (r=0.632 S.E. = 14.512, C.R. = 5.986, p=0.05) rise in the prevalence of use of Hybrid teaching. At p 0.05, There is an impact of Artificial Intelligence on Hybrid teaching

AI's primary function in the classroom is to facilitate automated academic and administrative processes, customized instruction, intelligent content, and constant availability. Artificial intelligence (AI) has, over time, made previously inaccessible subjects like health, the environment, etc., more readily available. Given India's potential for AI development, the country must incorporate technology into education to make the most of this opportunity and prepare India's youth for the future workforce. The results of the study show that Artificial intelligence impacts hybrid teaching by 60-65%. Now the question arises that whether Hybrid teaching is acceptable on large scale.

The blended learning basically involves face to face learning with the interaction being supplemented by online learning so as to give the learners’ flexibility and the

instructors an opportunity to review their teaching strategies in reaching all students [19]. If integrated within this model, the use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools will go a long way in changing the status of teaching and learning. On the following side, we explain several effects of the AI tools used on the blended learning approach[20].

Personalization: Ironically, among the effects of introducing AI tools in the hybrid teaching model is the flexibility to address learners individually. By use of AI tools, student performance can be monitored and data on which the student is weak on can be generated with recommendations on how they can perform better given [21]. Such approach to delivery of instruction is highly effective to the adapted students since they may easily reach unique solution to their problems. AIMS can also provide intelligent learning paths which may be a course that progresses a learner through content at various paces and yet is fully planned with a finite goal at its end as well [22].

Enhanced Communication: AI tools can also contribute to the interaction between students and teachers as well. Through the usage of the online grading system that can evaluate a task and give a feedback immediately, one is able to dedicate his/her time to paying individual attention [23]. Chatbot can also be used to reply some of the frequently asked questions to relieve educators of answering such questions. Also, with the help of different AI tools, students can work in group compositions and collaborate through different platforms, connecting students from different geographical areas, working in real-time mode on different projects and during discussions [24].

Improved Accessibility: The integrated face-to-face and online teaching modes present some challenges to students with disability in that they are denied equal access to resources. It can be overcome by the help of AI tools which offer the students to interact with the material in other forms [25]. For instance, the text to speech technologies can speak words in written documents thus making it easier for an impaired vision students to understand them. Language translation during hybrid learning is also possible through these AI tools hence making it easier for those who have no well understanding of the local language [26].

Increased Data-Driven Insights: AI tools in the presented scheme of the hybrid teaching model are also focused on the use of more data-based approaches to education. With big data collected and analysed, AI applications can detect what educators may not: details and structures helping to make accurate decisions about what should be taught, how it should be taught, and how classes should be administrated. This may lead to a positive change in terms of teacher delivery and reception of content by all students [27].

Increased Efficiency: Last but not the least, AI applications can play a significant role in minimizing paper works and taking care of time-consuming assignments that professing and faculty members often get bogged down with [28]. For

instance, in scheduling, there are AI based scheduling which helps in the scheduling of classes, meetings and events, and there is AI based attendance system, which track the students' attendance whether physical or online. This in turn can lead to better organization of the educational environment, production and reduction of stressful impacts on the educator [29].

Therefore, AI based tools can very much serve a purpose of enriching the overall learning and teaching paradigm within the employed hybrid model of approach [24]. Namely, through personalization, communication, access, data, and efficiency, AI can contribute to developing an attention, accessible, rich, analytical, and productive learning context. Given the current trends in practice advancement, it is for sure to note that the further application of AI innovation in education is doable as well as expansive [30].

VII. CONCLUSION

While many authors and government agencies have voiced their optimism that AI will free up teachers' time, others have argued that AI will eventually render teachers obsolete, or at the very least repurpose them as classroom orchestrators/technology facilitators whose responsibilities will include regulating student behaviour and making sure the technology is turned on. The truth is that much AIED research and development over the past 30 years has concentrated on employing AI to directly support learners with the purpose of boosting learning, typically by taking over instructor responsibilities, such as through AI-powered adaptive tutoring (. In that time period, artificial intelligence research aimed at aiding educators has received scant attention.

Tools to analyse and support educator practices, time management, and lesson planning have been developed, and AI has been used to scour the internet to compile useful information. However, few commercial players have adopted this, and few people have access to it. Over the course of many years, artificial intelligence tools have been developed with the goal of automatically assessing students' assignments, again primarily to free up teachers' time (nicely illustrating how the teacher-supporting/learner-supporting categories are not rigid, despite their usefulness). Australia scrapped plans to utilize automated marking for state-wide exams in 2018 out of worry that AI wouldn't be able to provide the same level of interpretation or analysis that human teachers would.

Implementing such a system would also neglect how much a teacher learns about their learners while reading what the learner has written, insights that no dashboard will ever supply. This is true even if AI were capable of fair and accurate marking of free writing. Possible avenues for research at the intersection of AI and education include programs that assist teachers in grading student work by providing them with suggestions and time-saving tools (that is, the teacher does the grading, the AI only supports that process). Another area of study is the use of AI to

formatively analyse assignments, providing feedback to students on how to refine their work before it is submitted for final, summative evaluation. While it's possible that AI may help teachers save time, there's scant data to support this claim, and it's also uncertain how it would affect student learning and retention.

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